
**The Academic Life of Students in Chetan Bhagat's Five Point Someone and
Abhijit Bhadury's Mediocre But Arrogant**

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Abstract:

In India, there are 28 states and 8 union territories. The students do admit themselves in the various educational institutes like IIT, IIM, Medical Colleges, Law Colleges, Universities and Colleges. The word 'campus' means the grounds and buildings of a school, college or university. The campus of these institutes occupies the premises of these concerned institutes. According to Chris Baldick campus novel is "a novel, usually comic or satirical, in which the action is set within enclosed world of university (or similar set of learning) and highlights the follies of academic life". The phrase 'campus novel' came into Oxford Dictionary in 1968. The campus novels do occupy the geographical premises of a school, college or university. The campus novel is also called as an academic life. The majority of action takes place in the campus premises of the educational institutes. It consists of classrooms, hostels, canteen, laboratory, library, etc. There is a unique life of professors, lecturers, students and non-teaching staff, which is narrated in a campus novel. The academic life of students includes education, friendship, love life, career anxiety, campus politics, hostel life, etc. Chetan Bhagat and Abhijit Bhaduri are the important campus novelists of 21st century. Both of them depict the academic life of students on the campuses of IIT Delhi and Management Institute of Jamshedpur respectively. The present research paper concentrates on the academic life of students in Chetan Bhagat's Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT (2004) and Abhijit Bhaduri's Mediocre But Arrogant (2012).

Keywords: *Campus Novel, Academic Life, Education, Friendship, Love Life, Career Anxiety, Hostel Life*

Introduction:

A campus novel is a sub-genre of novel where the main action is set in and around the campus of a college or university. It is also called an academic novel. It is an interesting genre that has gained the worldwide readership. The campuses spread throughout the world provide the rich productive raw material for this genre.

A campus novel, also known as academic novel, is a novel; its main action is set in and around the campus of a university and colleges. Majority of action

takes place in the campus premises of any university or college. It consists of classrooms, hostels, canteen, laboratory, library, etc. There is a unique life of professors, lecturers, students and non-teaching staff, which is narrated in a campus novel. The genre in its current form dates back to the early 1950s. *The Groves of Academe* by Mary McCarthy, published in 1952, is often quoted as the earliest example of an academic novel. Randall Jarell's *Pictures from an Institution* (1954), Vladimir Nabokov's *Pnin*, (1955) are the examples of academic novels. In Indian

context the first academic novel is *The Long Long Days* (1960) by P.M. Nityanandan. Other examples of Indian campus novels are *The Farewell Party* by M. V. Rama in (1971) and K. M. Trisanku's *Onion Peel* (1973), etc.

The academic life of students includes education, friendship, love life, career anxiety, campus politics, hostel life, etc. The present research paper concentrates on Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT* (2004) and Abhijit Bhaduri's *Mediocre But Arrogant* (2012).

The present research paper is an honest attempt to evaluate the academic life of students in the selected Indian English novels with reference to the works of Chetan Bhagat and Abhijit Bhaduri.

The Academic Life of Students in Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT* (2004) and Abhijit Bhaduri's *Mediocre But Arrogant* (2012):

Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT* (2004):

Chetan Bhagat is well-known Indian author, columnist, screenwriter and motivational speaker. He has completed his engineering and MBA from IIT Delhi and IIM Ahmedabad respectively. He was an investment banker at Goldman Sachs in Hong Kong but left this job after few years to pursue his passion in writing. He has penned five novels and three nonfiction books. The Time Magazine honored him including in the list of world's hundred most influential people in 2010. He is the most prominent campus novelist in twenty first century. *One Night @ Call Center* (2005),

The 3 Mistakes of My Life (2008), *2 States: The Story of my Marriage* (2009), *Revolution 2020* (2011), *Half Girlfriend* (2014), *One Indian Girl* (2016), *The Girl in Room 105* (2018), *One Arranged Murder* (2020), *400 Days* (2021), *What Young India Wants* (2012), *Making India Awesome* (2015), *India Positive* (2019) are his important books.

Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT was published in 2004. The novel is the trend setting novel of the 21st century. The campus of IIT Delhi is described in the novel. It narrates the story of three friends, Hari Kumar, Alok Gupta and Ryan Oberoi who find it difficult to improve their grades. Issues such as ragging, grading system, malpractices, pressures and tensions of academic life, students-teachers relationship, hostel life, careerism, are depicted in the novel. The film '3 Idiots' directed by Rajkumar Hirani which was released in 2009 is based on this novel.

Abhijit Bhaduri's *Mediocre But Arrogant* (2012):

Abhijit Bhaduri is an author, columnist and management consultant. He worked as a Chief Learning Officer for the Wipro Group. At present he works as a Human Resources professional in the U.S.A. He is also a successful cartoonist. He penned the books that is *Married But Available* (2008), *Don't Hire the Best* (2012), *The Digital Tsunami* (2016).

Mediocre But Arrogant was published in 2005. It is set at the Management Institute of Jamshedpur. It is the second book of the 'MBA' series which includes *Mediocre But Arrogant* and *Married But Available*. The novel is about the life of the protagonist, Abbey and his successful attempts in obtaining a job in HR.

It can be included under the bildungsroman category of campus novel.

career anxiety, campus politics and hostel life are focused in both of these novels.

Conclusion:

Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT (2004)* and Abhijit Bhaduri's *Mediocre But Arrogant (2012)* depict the academic life of students at the campuses of IIT Delhi and Management Institute of Jamshedpur respectively. The themes like education, friendship, love life,

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